

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES TO IMPROVE LEARNING PROCESS

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Аннотация: В данной статье изучаются педагогические проблемы диагностики дошкольников, использование диагностики в традиционном обучении и проверке знаний и умений учащихся, результаты экзаменов, объясняется их происхождение.

Ключевые слова: мониторинг, проверка, оценка, сбор статистических данных, их анализ, определение динамики, определение тенденций, прогнозирование дальнейшего развития.

Annotation: This article studies the pedagogical problems of diagnosing preschoolers, the use of diagnostics in traditional education and testing the knowledge and skills of students, exam results, and explains their origin.

Key words: monitoring, verification, evaluation, collection of statistical data, their analysis, determination of dynamics, determination of trends, forecasting of further development.

Preschool education and upbringing are inalienable, and they can only be conditionally separated in the course of the educational process. Educational programs for preschool children, in contrast to preschool education programs, include training and components related to organizing the life of children in a group. Therefore, the diagnosis of preschool age should be based only on the definition of knowledge and skills.

The problem of pedagogical diagnostics is several thousand years old, because from the very beginning of pedagogical activity, society had to evaluate the results of education. He constantly taught, always tried to determine the results of his actions.

The investment in diagnostics is greater than in traditional training and testing of trainees' knowledge and skills. The results of the examination are studied, explaining their origin.

Diagnostics studies the results in connection with methods, tools and achievements, determines the trends and dynamics of the formation of educational products.

Diagnostics includes control, examination, evaluation, collection of statistical data, their analysis, determination of dynamics, determination of trends, forecasting of further development.

Pedagogical diagnostics, firstly, to optimize the individual educational process, secondly, to ensure the correct determination of educational results, taking into account public interests, and thirdly, to separate children into one educational group, taking into account the developed criteria. aimed at minimizing transmission errors.

A set of specially selected and systematized tasks that allow children to:

- to determine the features of the assimilation of scientific knowledge and skills by children;

- determination of the essence of the child's difficulties and determination of their causes;

- determination of the level of mastery of educational activities;

- assessment of changes in the development of children.

Pedagogical diagnostics is aimed at assessing the following results:

- to have the ability to accept and support the goals and objectives of educational activities, to seek means of their implementation;

- development of creative and search methods for solving problems;

- the ability to plan, control and evaluate educational activities in accordance with the task and the conditions for its implementation; determine the most effective ways to achieve results;

- the ability to understand the reasons for success or failure in educational activities;

- skillfully study the logical actions of comparison, analysis, synthesis, generalization, classification, comparison and establishment of cause-and-effect relationships, the formation of logical thoughts.

Since the diagnostics of learning outcomes is an integral part of the educational process and is carried out through regular monitoring and accounting of the educational process, all diagnostic processes include control, training, training, development, promotion and serve to perform corrective functions.

The control and diagnostic function is associated with determining the level of assimilation of the material, its compliance with norms and standards.

The diagnostic function of learning is determined by the increase in knowledge and skills in the control process.

This diagnostic task is related to the fact that, as an element of the educational process, it consists not only in determining the level of training, but also, first of all, in teaching children, correcting mistakes, and helping them.

During the test, children listen and understand the answers of their friends, actively participate in the survey (ask questions, answer questions, repeat material to themselves), consolidate and deepen knowledge and skills, perform exercises, complete lessons, make additions. audition, etc.

The educational function is associated with the formation of sufficient self-awareness, responsibility, determination, discipline and other character traits.

The developing function is manifested in the development of speech, memory, thinking, etc. in the process of examination and evaluation.

Objective supervision motivates children to learn, inspires them and instills confidence in their future development.

The correctional function is associated with the pedagogical thinking of the teacher, his introspection, improvement of planning and organization of studies.

The main diagnostic functions are control and corrective, they have a number of tasks: to determine the knowledge and skills of each child; timely identification of gaps in knowledge and skills; identify the reasons for the low assimilation of some parts of the educational material; repetition and systematization of the studied; is indicated when determining the level of readiness for learning new material.

In a word, pedagogical diagnostics makes it possible to determine the characteristics of children's assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as the nature of children's difficulties, to establish their causes and eliminate them. Diagnostics, which serves to improve the educational process, should be focused on the following goals.

1. Internal and external correction in case of incorrect assessment of learning outcomes;
2. Identification of gaps in education; confirmation of successful learning outcomes;
3. Planning the next stages of the educational process;
4. Stimulation by increasing academic skills and regulating the complexity of the next stages;
5. Improvement of learning conditions.

Pedagogical diagnostics is a set of control and evaluation methods aimed at solving the problems of optimizing the educational process, differentiating children, as well as improving educational programs and methods of pedagogical influence.

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